

Educational Neglect

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Introduction

A child can be abused physically, sexually or mentally. It can be in the form of injury, neglect or negligent treatment, blaming, forced sexual stimulation and activity, incest exploitation and sexual abuse. Child abuse can take place in homes, schools, orphanages, residential care facilities, on the streets, in the workplace, in prisons and in places of detention.

53% of children in India face some form of child sexual abuse. According to the National Crime Records Bureau, the cases of rape and murder of children increase every year. The growing complexities of life and the changed social economic conditions have exposed the children to new and different forms of abuse. But the sad state of the affairs is that such heinous acts are reported less. It has such a psychological impact on the mind of the child that he seldom gathers the courage to speak about the act being committed against him. If even if he confides the fact with someone, the social factors let the fact being dumped under the fear of family reputation and other related issues. In fact child abuse is a violation of the basic human rights of a child.

Child Abuse is a physical, psychological harassment to a child by their parents or-else of caretakers. It also includes the leaving and neglecting of child or children by their own parents. Many NGO’s and Government rules are trying to reduce the Child Abuse, but unfortunately it was unable to stop totally in somewhat minimized. A Child has been compared like a god in India, but many people are harassing the child in both physically and mentally. Many children are facing physical harassment very badly, especially the girl children where they are facing sexual harassment too. Here we are submitting this article with the, in what ways the child has been abused, Government rules and regulation to protect the children from the child abuse.

Objectives

The main objective of this article is what the ways that the child has been abused are. The emotional depression of a child due to psychological abuse. The physical and mental causes which the children has been faced. The Government rules and policy act to protect child from the abuse, and the role of NGO’s in the child abuse.

Definition

Childhood, especially the years from 0–6, establishes the foundation of a person’s life. Emotional, physical and sexual abuse can have an impact across an entire lifetime. Abuse and neglect happen to young children and teenagers. Child abuse is any form of physical, emotional and/or sexual mistreatment or lack of care that causes injury or emotional damage to a child or youth

Types

Physical Abuse

Intentional use of physical force against the child that results in – or has a high likelihood of resulting in - harm for the child’s health, survival, development or dignity. This includes hitting, beating, kicking, shaking, biting, strangling, scalding, burning, poisoning and suffocating. Much physical violence against children in the home is inflicted with the object of punishing.

Corporal punishment involves hitting like smacking, slapping, spanking of children, with the hand or with an implement – whip, stick, belt, shoe, wooden spoon, etc. But it can also involve, for example, kicking, shaking or throwing children, scratching, pinching, biting, pulling hair or boxing ears, forcing children to stay in uncomfortable positions, burning, scalding or forced ingestion (for example, washing children’s mouths out with soap or forcing them to swallow hot spices).

Most nations with child abuse laws deem the deliberate infliction of serious injuries, or actions that place the child at obvious risk of serious injury or death, to be illegal. Bruises, scratches, burns, broken bones, lacerations - as well as repeated “mishaps,” and rough treatment that could cause physical injuries can be physical abuse. Multiple injuries or fractures at different stages of healing can raise suspicion of abuse.

Sexual Abuse

Child sexual abuse (CSA) is defined by the Keeping Children and Families Safe Act of 2003 and which involves

- (a) The employment, use, persuasion, inducement, enticement, or Coercion of any child to engage in, or assist any other person to engage in, any sexually explicit conduct or simulation of such conduct for the purpose of producing a visual depiction of such conduct
- (b) The rape, and in cases of caretaker or interfamilialrelationships, statutory rape, molestation, prostitution, or another form of sexual exploitation of children, or incest with children.

Child sexual exploitation includes ownership, production, and supply of sexually explicit images of children; using the Internet to lure children into sexual acts; prostitution of children; and child molestation.

Sexual Assault includes any attempted or competed sexual acts with a child or adult who is coerced or forced to engage against their volition. This includes forcible sex offences such as rape and sodomy.

Children under the age of 18 contribute to 44.4% of India’s current population, half of which are not provided with basic education, nutrition, and health (Indian National Family Health Survey 2005-2006). Furthermore, India’s vast population of children is susceptible to various forms of child maltreatment (Carson et al., 2013; Chawla, 2004; Deb, 2005, 2009; Priyabadini, 2007). Specifically, the problem of child sexual abuse (CSA) extends into India’s early history and is considered a deep-rooted societal concern (Deb, 2002, 2009; Deb and Mukherjee, 2009; Iravani, 2011). The heightened public awareness of child sex trafficking has become an important human rights issue for policy makers.

Psychological Abuse

Emotional and psychological abuse in children is defined as behaviours, speech, and actions of parents, caregivers, or other significant figures in a child’s life that have a negative mental impact on the child.

Examples of emotional abuse include

- name calling
- insulting
- threatening violence (even without carrying out threats)
- allowing children to witness the physical or emotional abuse of another
- withholding love, support, or guidance

It’s very difficult to know how common child emotional abuse is. A wide range of behaviours can be considered abusive, and all forms are thought to be underreported.

Child abuse occurs in all types of families. However, reported abuse appears to be most common in families that are

- having financial difficulties
- dealing with single parenthood
- experiencing (or have experienced) a divorce
- struggling with substance abuse issues

Signs of emotional abuse in a child may include

- being fearful of a parent
- saying they hate a parent
- talking badly about themselves (such as saying, “I’m stupid”)
- seeming emotionally immature when compared to peers
- exhibiting sudden changes in speech (such as stuttering)
- experiencing a sudden change in behaviour (such as doing poorly in school)

Signs in a parent or caregiver include

- showing little or no regard for the child
- talking badly about the child
- not touching or holding the child affectionately
- not tending to the child’s medical needs

Causes

Child abuse is a complex phenomenon with multiple causes. No single factor can be identified as to why some adults behave violently toward children. The World Health Organization (WHO) and the International Society for Prevention of Child Abuse and Neglect (ISPCAN) identify multiple factors at the level of the individual, their relationships, their local community, and their society at large that combine to influence the occurrence of child maltreatment. At the individual level, such factors include age, sex, and personal history, while at the level of society; factors contributing to child maltreatment include cultural norms encouraging harsh physical punishment of children, economic inequality, and the lack of social safety nets. WHO and ISPCAN state that understanding the complex interplay of various risk factors is vital for dealing with the problem of child maltreatment,

Parents who physically abuse their spouses are more likely than others to physically abuse their children. However, it is impossible to know whether marital strife is a cause of child abuse, or if both the marital strife and the abuse are caused by tendencies in the abuser. Sometimes, parents set expectations for their child that is clearly beyond the child’s capability. When parents’ expectations are far beyond what is appropriate to the child (e.g., preschool children who are expected to be

totally responsible for self-care or provision of nurturance to parents) the resulting frustration caused by the child’s non-compliance is believed to function as a contributory if not necessary cause of child abuse.

Children resulting from unintended pregnancies are more likely to be abused or neglected. Also, unintended pregnancies are more likely than intended pregnancies to be associated with abusive relationships, and there is an increased risk of physical violence during pregnancy. They also result in poorer maternal mental health, and lower mother-child relationship quality.

The Protection of Children from Sexual Offences (POCSO) Act

The Protection of Children from Sexual Offences (POCSO) Act, 2012 was enacted to provide a robust legal framework for the protection of children from offences of sexual assault, sexual harassment and pornography, while safeguarding the interest of the child at every stage of the judicial process. The framing of the Act seeks to put children first by making it easy to use by including mechanisms for child-friendly reporting, recording of evidence, investigation and speedy trial of offences through designated Special Courts. The new Act provides for a variety of offences under which an accused can be punished.

NGO’S

There are several NGO who rescuing and providing the necessary needs for the child who suffered from Abuse. Also many NGO’s are fighting against the child abuse.

Conclusion

The only way to minimize the Child Abuse is parenting their kids in the right way, it will lead to betterment of growth of their children. Since every child has a unique talent, Parents has to identify the talents in the child and must cultivate it without demotivating. Many sexual harassments also can be minimized, if the child growth should be in good society atmosphere.

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